

Distributed Radar Network with Polymer Microwave Fiber (PMF) Based Synchronization

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Abstract—Distributed radar networks provide numerous advantages, such as increased angular resolution and improved signal-to-noise ratio. However, the requirement of having the chirped local oscillator (f_{TX}) signal distributed to minimize the phase noise of the bi-static and multi-static responses of such networks increases their complexity and expenses. Our work shows that it is possible to synthesize the frequency-modulated continuous-wave signal in a central module and distribute it at $f_{TX}/2$ via polymer microwave fiber (PMF) to radar nodes operating in the 76–81 GHz band. Thus, we are able to fulfill the requirement of being a coherent distributed radar network as well as bring the cost down by using PMF for the $f_{TX}/2$ distribution. Furthermore, we compare the performances of the same PMF based radar network with a coaxial cable based radar network for $f_{TX}/2$ distribution, and the performances are comparable.

Index Terms—Distributed radar network, frequency-modulated continuous-wave (FMCW) radar, polymer microwave fiber (PMF), synchronization, multi-static radar.

I. INTRODUCTION

Radar sensors provide essential measurements that enable the estimation of multiple target properties, including range, azimuth and elevation angles, as well as radial velocities. Cooperative efforts between radar sensors, as demonstrated in [1], highlight the potential of collaborative systems that enhance environment sensing. The key to these systems lies in the utilization of distributed radar networks, which form a cohesive web of radar systems working coherently. These types of distributed radar networks offer significant advantages, for example by providing comprehensive up to 360° high-definition coverage of the sensor's surroundings. Other examples, like in [2], show that by integrating information from multiple radar modules within a coherent network, it is possible to improve the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), enhance target identification, increase robustness against miss detections and false targets, and even estimate the velocity vector of targets.

Radar networks offer numerous operational advantages. However, they do come with requirements of timing synchronization and the need to establish phase coherency between radar nodes within the network which necessitates increased system

complexity. Within a radar network, incoming signals can be distinguished as either mono-static or bi-static information. Mono-static responses occur when a single module both transmits and receives the signal, while bi-static responses involve the transmission of the signal by another radar module in the network. The primary objective behind achieving phase coherency is to minimize the adverse impact of phase noise on the bi-static and multi-static responses without the need for complex signal processing steps. Therefore, to realize its full potential, a distributed radar network requires coherent operation, entailing precise timing synchronization and distribution of the chirped local oscillator (f_{TX}) signal.

In this work, we present a coherent distributed multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) radar network with polymer microwave fiber (PMF) based chirped synchronization around $f_{TX}/2$, where the chirped signal is synthesized in a central module and distributed via rectangular core PMFs to the four radar nodes in the network. In comparison to the current technologies used for distribution of local oscillator (LO) signal, such as coaxial cables [2] or polymer optical fibers (PoF) [3], [4], PMF is cheaper and a simpler substitution for the $f_{TX}/2$ signal distribution in a coherent MIMO radar network.

In Section II, different radar network synchronization concepts and their dependencies are discussed. In Section III, the measurement setups are described, and in Section IV the results are discussed. Finally, in Section V the conclusions and future work are presented.

II. NETWORK TOPOLOGIES

Distributed radar networks can be set up using three main synchronization topologies: incoherent, loosely coupled, and coherent. These topologies offer different levels of hardware complexity, phase coherence, and performance characteristics.

Phase noise is a crucial performance parameter and a significant limitation of radar systems. It is widely recognized that phase noise raises the noise floor level around strong targets, resulting in the masking of weaker targets located nearby [5]. In distributed radar networks with multiple radars, the issue

of phase noise is more severe. The transmitted and received signals in bi-static responses exhibit uncorrelated phase (except in a coherent radar network topology), resulting in higher phase noise in the radar output signal [6]. Unlike in a homodyne frequency modulated continuous wave (FMCW) radar, where the mixing process in the receiver chain typically cancels out phase errors, there is generally no such phase error cancellation in distributed radar networks.

In incoherent radar networks, solely a trigger signal is distributed for each radar node to initiate transmission. Advantages include: no high-frequency signal distribution, flexible wired or wireless trigger signal distribution, and lower hardware complexity. However, the lack of phase correlation in bi-static responses increases phase noise in the radar output.

In loosely coupled radar networks, both a reference clock signal (in the range of several tens of MHz) and a trigger signal for ramp start are distributed. Advantages include: no high-frequency signal distribution and due to the distributed reference clock signal, an improved phase noise performance compared to incoherent radar networks. However, each radar node synthesizes its own FMCW signal, which still leads to considerable phase noise for bi-static responses.

In coherent radar networks as shown in Fig. 1, the FMCW signal is synthesized in one module and distributed to other radars via metallic waveguides, coaxial cables [2], PoF [3], etc. Achieving full coherency requires synchronization of reference clocks, ramp start, and analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) across all nodes in the distributed radar network. This synchronization ensures that the mono-static and bi-static responses exhibit similar phase noise characteristics. However, the downside of this network type is the increased hardware complexity.

For coherent radar networks, different chirped LO signal distribution technologies are available. In [2], a coherent radar network using coaxial cable for distribution at $f_{TX}/2$ is used. The authors of [3], employ a radar system where a central unit generates the FMCW ramp which is then converted to an optical signal and distributed at $f_{TX}/4$ through an analog optical channel. At the transmitters and receivers, the optical signal is converted back to the electrical domain. Also the authors of [4] use the optical domain to implement a radar network.

These technologies show various limitations. In the mm-

Fig. 1. Simplified block diagram of a distributed radar network.

wave spectrum, metallic waveguides are heavy, complex to fabricate, and offer limited flexibility. Metallic waveguides and coaxial cables are more expensive than PoF and PMF. However, PoF requires micrometer precision and costly optical-electrical conversion.

PMFs also known as dielectric waveguides are a technology that can transfer microwave signals. These low-loss and flexible fibers can guide high frequency electromagnetic (EM) waves. At sufficiently high frequencies the EM energy will be concentrated at the core of the fiber, but a small part of the field will propagate outside it. Therefore, it is important to have a low-loss cladding to ensure that the signal is not distorted. As the frequency is increased the cross section of the fiber scales down. At mm-wave frequencies, the required fiber diameter is comparable to that of copper and optical cables [7]. Furthermore, it is low-cost, less sensitive to temperature variations, low weight and mechanically robust [8], [9].

In our work we are using PMF for distribution of the chirped signal at $f_{TX}/2$ from the central module to the radar nodes in the network. The four identical rectangular foam PMFs made of Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) have a thickness of 3.1 mm, a width of 5.8 mm, and a length of 950 mm.

III. MEASUREMENT SETUP

In Fig. 2, the coherent MIMO FMCW radar network used for these experiments is presented. The FMCW signal is generated at $f_{TX}/2$ within the central module and then propagated through a microstrip line to the waveguides housed within the central module. These waveguides establish a connection to the PMFs. The synthesized FMCW signal (expressed as $f_{TX}/2$) is transmitted via the PMFs (38–40.5 GHz) subsequently to the four distributed radar nodes in the network.

Upon reaching the radar nodes, the received $f_{TX}/2$ signal is conveyed via waveguides and transmitted through a microstrip

Fig. 2. Distributed radar network with PMF based chirped LO synchronization.

Fig. 3. Cross-section of PMF with cladding and waveguide transition.

Fig. 4. S-parameter measurement setup.

line to the Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuits (MMICs) at each radar node, where the signal is unconverted and transmitted via antennas. For full coherency, it is important for the central module to distribute the reference clock, ADC synchronization signal, ramp trigger signal, and a field programmable gate array (FPGA) trigger signal. These moderate-frequency signals are transmitted as differential signals via twisted pair cables.

In Fig. 3, a detailed cross-sectional illustration depicts the connection of PMF to a waveguide, highlighting the presence of cladding and a waveguide transition in the assembly at the central module and at the radar nodes.

To prevent the chirped $f_{TX}/2$ signal from being distorted, it is important that there is no contact between the PMFs to avoid cross-talk and contact with any other object in the vicinity, since not the whole PMF is encased in cladding. Furthermore, care has to be taken to keep the bending radius of the PMFs to a minimum to prevent the EM wave energy from propagating out of the core.

To evaluate the performance of the distributed radar network with PMF synchronization, we used the same distributed radar network and replaced the PMF with coaxial cables and performed the same measurements.

The parameters of the radar network are: start frequency 76.5 GHz, sweep bandwidth 900 MHz, sweep time 64 μ s, and 512 intermediate frequency (IF) samples. For the transmit channel separation in the MIMO radar network, Doppler modulation as described in [2] is used.

S-parameter measurements were conducted using an Agilent Technologies E8364A PNA series network analyzer, covering a frequency range from 45 MHz–50 GHz. The Devices Under Test (DUTs) were connected to the network analyzer according to the configuration illustrated in Figure 4. To ensure the accuracy of our measurements, we performed calibration at the end of the 2.4 mm coaxial cable connections. This calibration involved open, short and transmission standards. The measured coaxial cable had a 2.4 mm connection, directly interfacing with the network analyzer cables.

For the PMF measurements, the setup had to be slightly modified. The network analyzer’s coaxial cable was connected to a coaxial-to-waveguide adapter, and the PMF was connected to the waveguides for the S-parameter measurements. To de-embed the effects of the coaxial-to-waveguide transitions, we perform a reference measurement by connecting two waveguide-to-coaxial adapters back-to-back and measured the S-parameters. Subsequently we applied these reference measurements to de-embed the S-parameters obtained from the PMF measurements [10], [11].

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Fig. 5, the measured loss for the PMF cable used is compared to the loss of a coaxial cable. It is possible to observe that PMF has higher losses compared to the coaxial cable, however it is within the tolerance level of this distributed radar network. Furthermore, the PMF dispersion does not severely impact the system as will be seen with the measurement results. This means the network is completely functional without having to use any additional components to boost the chirped $f_{TX}/2$ signal. Note that the non-perfect transitions between vector network analyzer (VNA) connectors and dielectric waveguides lead to some ripple, which could be reduced by an optimized transition.

Fig. 5. The attenuation and group-delay for PMF and coaxial cable are compared. It is possible to observe that PMF has higher losses compared to the coaxial cable, however this loss is at an acceptable level for the components used in the network.

The measurements presented are for the scenario in Fig. 6. In Fig. 7, the bi-static range profiles for the PMF based radar network and coaxial cable based radar network are compared, while in Fig. 8 the data processed based on the approach presented in [2] for the two networks are presented. From these results, it is evident that the proposed PMF based chirped

$\sqrt{f_{TX}}$ synchronization network performs as well as the coaxial cable based network.

Fig. 6. A metallic cylinder has been placed along the center line of the network and a corner reflector is located in front of module 4.

Fig. 7. The range profiles of the bi-static responses of module 4 for the measurement scenario in Fig. 6. Comparable performance is achieved.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have shown that it is possible to use PMF based chirped $\sqrt{f_{TX}}$ synchronization for distributed radar networks with comparable performances to radar networks with chirped $\sqrt{f_{TX}}$ distributed via coaxial cables. Due to the properties of PMF, it is possible to distribute at frequencies close to $\sqrt{f_{TX}}$ instead of a divided LO, at an inexpensive price compared to other technologies. Distribution at $\sqrt{f_{TX}}$ eliminates the effects of dividers/multipliers on the distributed signal. In the next step, a coherent distributed MIMO FMCW radar network with PMF based chirp distribution at $\sqrt{f_{TX}}$ is planned.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Gottinger, M. Hoffmann, M. Christmann, M. Schütz, F. Kirsch, P. Gulden, and M. Vossiek, "Coherent automotive radar networks: the next generation of radar-based imaging and mapping," *IEEE Journal of Microwaves*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 149–163, 2021.
- [2] S. L. Fernández, A. C. J. Samarasekera, R. Feger, and A. Stelzer, "Measurement-based analysis of a non-coherent MIMO radar network for automotive applications," in *2022 19th European Radar Conference (EuRAD)*, Sep. 2022, pp. 1–4.
- [3] C. Höhn, C. C. aliskan, S. Kupijai, H. Rhee, U. Keil, T. Gisder, M.-M. Meinecke, and H. G. Kurz, "Photonic radar system considerations for an analog optical channel," in *2023 24th International Radar Symposium (IRS)*, May 2023, pp. 1–8.
- [4] S. Kruse, P. Kneuper, T. Schwabe, M.-M. Meinecke, H. G. Kurz, and J. C. Scheytt, "Distributed system architecture for software-defined radio / radar with optical signal distribution," in *2023 24th International Radar Symposium (IRS)*, May 2023, pp. 1–8.
- [5] M. Budge and M. Burt, "Range correlation effects in radars," in *The Record of the 1993 IEEE National Radar Conference*, 1993, pp. 212–216.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. The comparison of distributed radar networks with (a) coaxial cable synchronization and (b) PMF synchronization show similar results for range and cross range processing.

- [6] A. Frischen, J. Hasch, and C. Waldschmidt, "Performance degradation in cooperative radar sensor systems due to uncorrelated phase noise," in *2014 11th European Radar Conference*, 2014, pp. 241–244.
- [7] M. De Wit, S. Ooms, B. Philippe, Y. Zhang, and P. Reynaert, "Polymer microwave fibers: a new approach that blends wireline, optical, and wireless communication," *IEEE Microwave Magazine*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 51–66, Jan 2020.
- [8] F. Strömbeck, Y. Yan, and H. Zirath, "A beyond 100-Gbps polymer microwave fiber communication link at D-band," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 70, no. 7, pp. 3017–3028, July 2023.
- [9] P. Reynaert, K. Dens, C. D'heer, D. Simic, J. Vaes, B. Philippe, and S. Ooms, "Polymer microwave fiber: a new communication concept that blends wireless, wireline and optical communication," in *2019 26th IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Circuits and Systems (ICECS)*, Nov 2019, pp. 755–758.
- [10] D. Frickey, "Conversions between s, z, y, h, abcd, and t parameters which are valid for complex source and load impedances," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 205–211, Feb 1994.
- [11] J. Frei, X.-D. Cai, and S. Müller, "Multiport s-parameter and t-parameter conversion with symmetry extension," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 56, no. 11, pp. 2493–2504, Nov 2008.